

Farmer Clusters for Realising Agrobiodiversity
Management across Europe

Farmer Cluster Activity Briefs:

Documentation of farmer-based biodiversity observation and monitoring activities between 2021 and 2024 in 11 FRAMEwork Farmer Clusters across Europe.

Gerid Hager, Daniela Ablinger, Virginia Bagnoni, Gillian Banks, Graham Begg, Marco Beyer, Iris C. Bohnet, Clare Buckerfield, Alice Caselli, Cyrille Charles, Kristina Janečková, Riina Kaasik, Youri Martin, Niamh McHugh, Camilla Moonen, Ellie Ness, Aliyeh Salehi, Martine Schoone, Jan Trávníček, Paul van Rijn, Gonzalo Varas, Eve Veromann, Silva Vilumets, François Warlop, Marie-Luise Wohlmuth

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Introduction

The FRAMEwork project took a bottom-up and action-based research approach to developing biodiversity and ecosystem services (ES) observation and monitoring activities with farmers in 11 Farmer Clusters (FCs) across nine European countries. This approach was chosen to cater directly to the real-world context of the farmers, as well as their interests and needs in terms of biodiversity and ES. In total, about 70 events and activities were organised between autumn 2021 and 2024 across the 11 FCs, with more than 1,000 attendances of farmers and other local participants.

This supplementary document contains a full documentation of these activities via activity briefs. First, the activity brief template is presented, which was used as a basis for activity documentation. Then follow the completed activity briefs for each FRAMEwork FC documenting activities held in the FCs to engage farmers in observing biodiversity and ES. Additional insights and information in the form of short stories and news about these activities published by FC partners can be accessed on the [Recodo online platform](#).

Associated protocols, apps and tools mentioned in the activity briefs are documented in the [FRAMEwork collection of citizen science protocols and materials](#) on Zenodo.

Activity brief – Template

Creator: Gerid Hager (IIASA)

Name of activity
Purpose and goals of activity
Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers <i>What happened during the activity, how did the activity unfold, sequence of events</i>
Participants <i>Who were the participants, how many farmers and other participants (if applicable)</i>
Duration <i>When and how long did the activity take place (one day, several weeks/months, ongoing since... etc.)?</i>
Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>List any digital apps and tools used by the farmers to conduct the activity. Add links to apps or app websites for more info.</i> • <i>List other materials, protocols, step-by-step guidelines etc. given to the farmers and share the documents.</i> • <i>If no materials were used, describe how the farmers were trained or supported to conduct the activity (on-site demos, peer exchange between farmers, etc.)</i>
Data collected <i>Describe if and how data was collected, in which form, where the data sits and who has access to the data.</i>
Images <i>Share images of the activity on-site and of the apps/tools used (e.g., app screenshots)</i>
Partners <i>List any external partners not participating in FRAMEwork project (names and/or organizations) that you collaborated with to conduct the activity. If available, share a link to their website.</i>
Future plans <i>Share any plans for continuation, follow-up or derivative activities that can be associated with this activity.</i>

Activity briefs – Basse-Durance Farmer Cluster, France

Creator: François Warlop (GRAB)

Predation assessment with predation cards

Purpose and goals of activity

The objective is to show farmers relevance of simple flower strips, effects on beneficial fauna, and on pest control in orchards.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Flower strips have been sown during fall/winter 2022/2023 and 2023/2024 with mustard, Phacelia, alfalfa. In spring, GRAB brought predation cards (made with codling moth eggs) and hang them in flower strips, in orchard first and second rows, to see how beneficial insects move in orchard. Several plots belonging to different farmers have been used. A few days later, farmers were asked to come and observe predation cards, to measure predation rate in the different locations and conclude about flower strip effect. 5 flower strips have been sown between October 2022 and January 2023. Only 2 flower strips are developed enough in March. Five predation cards per treatment have been exposed for 3 days, from 21 to 24th of March. Here are the first results of cards reading. One farmer joined for this observation (picture). In 2024, following autumn sowings, most flower strips started to bloom in March 2024 for early species. At the end of April, GRAB set up predation cards in strips and in orchards for farmers to observe different levels of natural regulation, like in 2023.

Participants

3 farmers participated in the observation activity in 2023 (photo), and only one in 2024 because of very complicated weather conditions leading to higher workload.

Images

Duration

This activity took place between March and May in 2023 and 2024. It takes half a day to set up cards, and 2 hours to read them, depending on the number of cards.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

No material is needed excepted predation cards with insect eggs. Farmers were taught directly in the field for eggs observation with a loop.

Data collected

Data have been collected and reported by GRAB on Excel.

<p>Partners INRAE provide codling moth eggs free of charge.</p>
<p>Future plans No future plans.</p>

Bat box observation (summertime)

<p>Purpose and goals of activity Batbox observation aims to measure occupation over time and its effectiveness to reduce fruit damages.</p>
<p>Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers Mapping of boxes for each farmer has been prepared, printed and given to farmers during a dedicated meeting. Endoscopic cameras have been bought to ease observation inside boxes during the day. Farmers have been explained how to use maps and cameras (photo).</p>
<p>Participants Several farmers used the cameras and observed (part of) boxes during summer/fall 2023. A public event was also proposed in October 2023 for students and wider public to teach them about importance of bats for agriculture.</p>
<p>Duration For each farmer, activity takes about half a day to observe bat boxes, according to number of boxes.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A map and notation grid were given to each participating farmer. • Endoscopic cameras were used for this purpose, available at e.g., depstech.com.
<p>Data collected Data have been collected by some farmers (few ones) and has not been sent back to GRAB.</p>

Images

<p>Partners Groupe Chiroptères de Provence partnered in the public event: https://www.gcprovence.org/ https://www.fetedelascience.fr/observation-de-gites-chauve-souris</p>
<p>Future plans Farmers' training allows observations activity to continue on an individual basis after projects ends.</p>

Bird nests observation (wintertime)
<p>Purpose and goals of activity Bird nest observations measure occupation over time and its effectiveness to reduce fruit damages.</p>
<p>Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers Mapping of nests of blue tits for each farmer has been prepared, printed and given to farmers. These nests must be cleaned every winter to be useful in following season. By cleaning nests, farmers can observe what kind of occupation has occurred: tit, other bird, wasps, spiders, etc.</p>
<p>Participants Farmers from the Farmer Cluster. A few have reported to monitor nests in winter.</p>
<p>Duration For each farmer, activity takes about half a day to observe nests, according to their number, but this time has to be spent for keeping nests operational.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A map and corresponding grid were given to each participating farmer.
<p>Data collected Data have been collected by a few farmers but have not yet been sent to GRAB.</p>
<p>Images No images available.</p>
<p>Partners No external partners.</p>
<p>Future plans Farmers' training allows observations activity to continue on an individual basis after projects ends.</p>

Bat boxes and bird nests settlement in orchards
<p>Purpose and goals of activity Set up homogenous density of batboxes/nests in orchards to observe their occupation throughout time and see potential effects on apple pests, especially moths.</p>
<p>Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers Our subcontractor Agrinichoires met farmers to decide about plots to be installed with batboxes. Then he organized the whole installation himself with colleagues.</p>
<p>Participants Agrinichoires set up the nests and boxes, farmers were not directly involved but they agreed to the process.</p>
<p>Duration It took 2 days to set up all batboxes and bird nests.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.) There are no associated protocols, apps and tools.</p>
<p>Data collected Occupation has been measured once in 2022 and 2023 by Agrinichoires. Information was shared with INRAE.</p>
<p>Images No images available</p>
<p>Partners Agrinichoires: https://agrinichoires.fr/</p>
<p>Future plans Associated activities see above.</p>

Activity briefs – Born Farmer Cluster, Luxembourg

Creators: Youri Martin, Cyrille Charles and Marco Beyer (LIST)

Wildlife camera traps in orchards and monitoring with farmers

Purpose and goals of activity

- Involve farmers of the cluster in biodiversity monitoring.
- Reveal another facet of biodiversity in orchards with nocturnal animals less known.
- Complement the database of citizen science data collected at the level of the FC with the City Nature Challenge.
- Complement the scientific biodiversity monitoring.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The camera trap activity was introduced to the farmers in October 2022. The interest of the action for the promotion of their orchards and the science knowledge was presented. The first phase of the activity, that is now closed, was the collection of the biodiversity data in the field with farmers. The facilitator has organised a small training for the installing and setting of the camera traps on the field with the battery maintenance and the downloading of the pictures from the SD card of the cameras. The camera traps were finally handed to 6 volunteer farmers who agreed to install them on their properties and take care of changing the memory cards. Some farmers were more involved in the camera traps maintenance than others and the supervision of a researcher from LIST was necessary to ensure the collection and the backup of the data. The 11 camera traps captured more than 54 000 pictures between October 2022 and December 2023. The second phase of the activity, still ongoing, is the involvement of farmers and citizens in the sorting of the pictures. In March 2024, the farmers were trained and invited to test the Picture Pile application for handling this vast number of images. Picture Pile is an application created by the NODES group at the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis in Austria that allows many people to participate in the analysis of visual research data. The app should help with one important first step in the data analysis, which is separating images showing wildlife in the orchards from images without wildlife (e.g., false triggering and all-black night shots, photos with livestock, domestic animals, vehicles, hikers etc). The third and last phase of the activity, not yet started, is the analysis of the biodiversity data collected and the use of the results for publications and communication with the FC.

Recodo news to inform the farmers about the use of Picture Pile <https://recodo.io/news/farmer-cluster/3a108bfc-97d8-c86a-bdc3-0ceb479642>

Participants

We have engaged 6 farmers in this activity and 11 camera traps were used.

The use of the Picture Pile application for the image sorting was tested in priority with farmers but could now be more widely open to all the citizens.

Duration

The first phase of the activity for the camera traps recording on the field took place from October 2022 to December 2023. The second phase for the pictures sorting and pre-analysis started in January 2024 and is ongoing. The third phase of the activity for the analysis and the use of the results has not started yet.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

The farmers were trained on site directly with the camera traps (see pictures below) and via an accompanying presentation. Furthermore, we used the following applications:

- Picture Pile application created by the NODES group at the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis in Austria <https://pppui.cloud.geo-wiki.org/webapp/>
- Agouti for the scientific use and analysis of the pictures: <https://www.agouti.eu/>

Images

Data collected

More than 54 000 pictures were collected. They are stored in the file server of the LIST institution sorted by location in the orchards and ID of the camera trap used. They will be imported in the Agouti software for further analysis. Only LIST has access to the full pictures database. For the moment, 5000 pictures are also uploaded in Picture Pile to be sorted by the farmers.

Partners

Ramborn Cider Company, L-6660 Born, <https://www.ramborn.com/>

Future plans

- Further assess the utility of Picture Pile.
- Uploaded all pictures in Agouti for species determination and database generation for analysis.
- Come back with the results to the FC (farmers and Ramborn).
- Assess potential to write a publication (Biodiversity captured by camera traps in apple trees).

Three years of City Nature Challenge in the Born Farmer Cluster

Purpose and goals of activity

- Promote the farmer cluster at the regional level
- Involve citizens (including farmers) into biodiversity monitoring activities
- Since biodiversity cannot be filled into a bottle and be brought to the customers, the customers were brought to the biodiversity within the orchards used for cider production.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The citizen science event “City Nature Challenge” was organized in the area of the Born cluster in the years 2022, 2023 and 2024. The local stakeholder Ramborn Cider Co. provided a base camp for the event organized with the scientists of LIST, Bee-together and the Natur-& Geopark Mëllerdall, where participants were welcomed and made familiar with the app iNaturalist that was used for recording the data. The citizens were invited to follow a walking path through the orchards where they could meet scientists at different locations to help making naturalist observations and discuss about biodiversity. Several guided tours with scientists and farmers to observe biodiversity and discuss about the orchards management were also organised. Our activity at Born took place in the framework of the national CNC event lead by the Musée National d’Histoire Naturelle du Luxembourg (MNHNL).

Participants

The number of participants that joined us for the event was ~300 in 2022, ~150 in 2023 and ~180 in 2024. Around 3 to 6 farmers joined us every year. The number of participants that uploaded their observations to the platform iNaturalist was 72 in 2022, 46 in 2023 and 60 in 2024. On average, each active participant provided between 6 and 8 observations. Three observers contributed in 2022 and 2023, four contributed in 2022 and 2024, five contributed in 2023 and 2024 and 2 observers contributed in all years.

Duration

Even though the worldwide City Nature Challenge was longer, two consecutive days at the end of April / beginning of May were selected for the event in the Born cluster in each year. These days were: 30/04/2022, 01/05/2022, 29/04/2023, 30/04/2023, 27/04/2024 and 28/04/2024.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- The digital app used to train citizens and farmers was iNaturalist: <https://inaturalist.lu/>
- The citizens and farmers were train on the day of the event with a PPT presentation and a speaker from LIST explaining the use of the iNaturalist app, the goal of the day and the hiking tour to follow. Scientists were also available at specific locations on the hiking tour to meet and help citizens. Guided tour with scientists and farmers were also organised.

Data collected

In the cluster area, 859, 339 and 839 observations were obtained for the years 2022, 2023 and 2024, respectively and 22, 109 and 19 observations were obtained in the control area for 2022, 2023 and 2024, respectively. The total number of observations was thus 2187.

Number and location of observations in 2022, 2023 and 2024. Each yellow point is one observation. The southern group of points is located in the farmer cluster area, while the northern group of points is located in the control area. Yellow numbers indicate the number of observations.

The platform iNaturalist classifies uploaded observations either as “casual”, if the identification of the organism is uncertain, or as “needs id”, if no identification was suggested, so far, or as “research” if at least two persons came to the same conclusion regarding the taxonomic identity of the organism of the record. More than 50 observations with research grade were acquired each day. For the following analyses, only the research grade observations will be used. The total number of research grade observations as of 07/08/2024 was 1003. Since only 82 research grade observations were available from the control area, the following analyses will be based on the remaining 921 research grade observations from the cluster area. In each year, most observations were classified as Plantae, followed by Insectae. Depending on year, Aves, Mollusca and Fungi played a significant role. Reptilia, Animalia, Mammalia and Amphibia were reported rarely.

Composition of iconic taxa of the observations made by citizen scientists during the City Nature Challenges 2022-2024 in the born cluster area.

Images

Impression from the City Nature Challenge 2023 in the orchards of the Born cluster.

A

B

C

Impressions from the City Nature Challenge 2024 carried out in the area of the Born cluster. (A) Briefing of the visitors at the base station. (B) Citizen scientist taking a picture of a Poaceae in bloom. (C) Larva of a newt in a drainage ditch.

Partners

- Musée national d'histoire naturelle Luxembourg (MNHN), L-2160 Luxembourg, <https://www.mnhn.lu/>
- Natur-& Geopark Mëlldall, L-6315 Beaufort, <https://www.naturpark-mellerdall.lu/>
- Bee Together, <https://beetogetherlux.wordpress.com/>
- Ramborn Cider Company, L-6660 Born, <https://www.ramborn.com/>

Future plans

- Let Ramborn and other partners continue the organisation of the event after the Framework project (LIST scientists may still be involved subject to available funding)
- Involve more schools.

Analysis of data for potential publications:

- Participant features based on the complete data set.
- Biodiversity features based on the research grade data.
- Complementarity of expert-obtained vs. citizens data collected on the FC area.
- Lessons learned from the BioBlitz events organised across FC in Europe.

Activity briefs – Buchan Farmer Cluster, UK

Creators: Gillian Banks and Graham Begg (JHI)

Aden Country Park and Buchan Farmer Cluster BioBlitz

Purpose and goals of activity

- Introduce farmers to citizen science and BioBlitz activities.
- Introduce visitors to the importance of biodiversity in farming systems, the idea of Farmer Clusters, and to the local Buchan Farmer Cluster.
- Raise awareness in the cluster farmers to the potential level of interest of the local community toward their activities.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The BioBlitz took place as part of a wellbeing festival hosted by the Aden Country Park. The festival was organized by the Aberdeenshire Council and included several organisations offering a variety of activities. The BioBlitz incorporated 4 community (vegetation, soil and worms, minibeast, birds) specific activities, staffed by experts from the James Hutton institute, NatureScot, and the Scottish Wildlife Trust. On arrival at the welcome stand, which was staffed by the FRAMEwork coordinator and the lead farmer from the Buchan Cluster, visitors were introduced to the planned BioBlitz activities, the timing and location of activities and the use of the iNaturalist app. The background of the FRAMEwork project, Farmer Cluster and the Buchan Farmer Cluster was also explained. At the BioBlitz stands, each of which was staffed by a participant in the FRAMEwork project (i.e., cluster farmers, cluster facilitator, survey staff), the visitors were introduced to the plants or animals being considered. This included the demonstration of the more common species using live samples or printed material. At the 'Vegetation Safari', 'Brilliant Birds', and 'Marvelous Minibeast' stands visitors were then able to walk a transect or search the area and were supported by experts in making and recording species observations. At the 'Wonderful Worms and Super Soil' stand, visitors were introduced to a method for the visual evaluation of soil structure and then to sampling soil for earthworms. Each of these activities were presented to groups of visitors on 6 occasions throughout the day. In addition, visitors were encouraged to explore three areas within the park using the iNaturalist app to make and record observations of plants and animals. At each stand visitors were given a sticker to add to a BioBlitz passport. Visitors were encouraged to return to the Welcome stand on completing the BioBlitz where they were given a completion certificate and invited to talk about what they had done and learnt, and to provide feedback.

Participants

Three farmers from the Buchan Farmer Cluster participated in the event. Hundreds of visitors attended but exact participation numbers were not recorded for the BioBlitz.

Duration

The BioBlitz took place on the 20th May 2023 from 11.00 to 15.00 at the Aden Country Park.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

A range of material was prepared to engage visitors and guide them through the BioBlitz activities, to support using the iNaturalist app, and carrying out activities at the soil BioBlitz stand.

- BioBlitz engagement guide (see image below)
- iNaturalist app
- [Guide to uploading and using the iNaturalist app](#)
- Instructions for conducting an earthworm survey based on the UkSoils.org [#30minworms resource](#)
- Instructions for visual [examination of soil structure \(VESS\)](#) based on the AHDB resource

Data collected

Visitors were given the opportunity to record their observations using paper record sheets (bird surveying) or using the iNaturalist app. In the area of the ‘Biodiversity in the Aden Country Park area of Aberdeenshire, Scotland’, 1422 observations of 459 species have been made by the [iNaturalist community](#). During the BioBlitz, 55 observations were shared of 48 species.

Images

Event material including BioBlitz mapping showing the location of the welcome stand and 4 community specific biodiversity stands, posters for the biodiversity stands and the BioBlitz sticker passport and sticker.

Partners

The Aden Country Park wellbeing festival was organised by Aberdeenshire Council. Daniel Bean Freelance Ecological Consultant participated in the BioBlitz staffing the Brilliant Birds stand and providing expertise in farmland birds. The Scottish Wildlife Trust participated in the BioBlitz staffing the Brilliant Birds stand and providing expertise in invertebrates.

Future plans

A further BioBlitz is being considered, adapting the activities carried out to enable the invitation of a visitor group (e.g., school, Girl Guides, etc.) to the Buchan Cluster as a more efficient approach.

Wild edible plants identification walk and talk

Purpose and goals of activity

To show that wild edible plants are more than weeds and to allow farmers to meet informally as a group.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Introduction to wild edible plants and mushrooms around a farm in St Combs and a Wild Edible BBQ including nettle soup, “weed” burgers, rhubarb and cicely crumble, and jelly ear mushrooms soaked in orange and covered in chocolate. The activities included a quiz followed by a walk to look at wild edible plants and areas on the farm that have been sown to encourage pollinators.

For the quiz, the farmers were divided into 2 teams and asked to identify 20 edible weeds from sample such as common hogweed and chickweed that had been gathered from the farm at the beginning of the event. The team correctly identifying the most species were the winners receiving a small prize of lager/beer. As each weed was identified, their edibility and potential medicinal properties were discussed. The farmers were also given a small container of plantain salve which has antibacterial properties and can be used for skin irritation, and to treat minor cuts, insect bites and stings. The quiz was followed by the farm walk with the aim of finding and identifying edible wild plants and mushrooms. The walk provided an opportunity for the cluster facilitator and farmers to discuss further the positive aspects of “weeds” and other components of farmland biodiversity. One of the farmers used an app (PlantNet) to help identify some of the plants on the walk. In addition, the group had a look at some cover crops consisting of “sand vetch”. The BBQ provided an enjoyable social element to the event and an opportunity for the facilitator to update the farmers on the biodiversity monitoring that was taking place and for the facilitator to meet one of the farmer’s agronomists.

The event was different to the usual event that the farmers attend. It aimed to show them that the plants that they call “weeds” can be useful as a food source or that they may have other uses such as producing fibres. All who attended enjoyed the relaxed atmosphere and felt they benefitted from the event – and gained a greater appreciation of the wild plants on their farms.

Participants

Cluster farmers and family, nine participants in total.

Duration

29th March 2022, St Combs, Aberdeenshire.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

There are no associated protocols, apps and tools to support observation activities. However, there was a Wild Edible Menu (Starter: Nettle soup; Main: Wild edible burgers and wild edible salad (Beef burgers or pork sausages available for the faint hearted; Dessert: Rhubarb crumble sweetened with wild cicely or Jelly Ears soaked in orange covered in chocolate.)

Data collected

No data was collected.

Images

Jelly ear mushrooms and ‘wild’ plants in a field margin at St Comb’s farm.

Partners

No external partners were engaged in the event.

Future plans

Wild edible treats and snacks to be provided at future Cluster meetings and events.

Earthworm sampling workshop

Purpose and goals of activity

To demonstrate an easy way for farmers to understand and observe earthworm activity on their fields.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The 30min worm survey was trialed on one cluster farm.

Participants

2 cluster farmers

Duration

One afternoon, Oct 2021

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

#30minworms survey method

Data collected

No data was collected.

Images

Partners

No external partners.

Future plans

No future plans.

Activity briefs – Burgenland Farmer Cluster, Austria

Creators: Marie-Luise Wohlmuth and Aliyeh Salehi (BOKU)

Co-development of monitoring of key species
<p>Purpose and goals of activity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity awareness training for cluster farmers and other farmers participating in the ÖKL event. • Joint identification of key species to complement and expand on the Austrian ÖPUL monitoring. • Active and recurring engagement of farmers in observing biodiversity on their land.
<p>Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers</p> <p>The activity started in May 2023 with an online meeting and a 1,5-hour workshop on-site to collectively select appropriate species to be monitored by each farmer during 2023-2025. Information about suitable species that have specific functions on arable land was prepared in advance with the help of experts. In the meeting, we decided to monitor one butterfly, the “Queen of Spain fritillary” (German name: Kleiner Perlmutterfalter), as it is a very important butterfly on farmland and indicates extensive management and biodiversity. At the request of farmers, one plant was added. The “Stachys arvensis” (German name: Ackerziest), a plant that was very common a few decades ago on arable land, then disappeared and is reappearing in recent years. After this meeting, the preparation of specific information material of the selected species was started, and suitable monitoring methods were developed. For this purpose, existing programs were consulted, and the methods used in them were adapted to our monitoring. The observation and monitoring methods were explained and demonstrated. The protocol was discussed, as well as the respective location and time period for the implementation. Each cluster farmer received a folder with all the information, protocol and species identification keys. During the second information meeting of the ÖKL (Austrian Board of Trustees for Agricultural Engineering and Rural Development) for biodiversity monitoring on 6th July 2023, we started the rollout for our additional monitoring after the ÖKL part, on the one hand with our cluster farmers and on the other hand with interested farmers who participated in the information meeting. All materials necessary for the monitoring were provided to the cluster farmers.</p>
<p>Participants</p> <p>Cluster farmers and other farmers participating in ÖPUL monitoring.</p>
<p>Duration</p> <p>The activity started in May 2023 and is ongoing.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification keys for key species in the Seewinkel region, sensitive to environmental stresses. • Observation protocol and data collection sheet.
<p>Data collected</p> <p>Data was collected in 2023, is ongoing in 2024 and will be collected in 2025 on all Cluster farms. Data is collected on paper sheets by the farmers, which will then be collated and discussed during joint meetings.</p>
<p>Images</p>

Partners

ÖKL Austrian Council for Agricultural Engineering and Rural Development
 ÖKL has integrated this topic into the training programme for farmers participating in the ÖPUL biodiversity monitoring programme.

Future plans

This activity is ongoing from 2023-2025.

Wild bee exhibition

Purpose and goals of activity

The great and important role of the wild bee for pollination should be better recognized in society.

Description of activity, implementation on-site

Walls were equipped with information boards and pictures about wild bees, with options for the garden to promote wild bees and information and pictures about measures that can be taken in and around arable fields to create a habitat for wild bees. In addition, a habitat table was created showing the different habitats for wild bees to breed. A table with information material and flyers was set up. The exhibition was supervised, and visitors were guided through the exhibition.

<p>Participants About 100 farmers who visited the Mostviertel Farmer Cluster event at Aubauernhof.</p>
<p>Duration 1 day in May 2023.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pictures and short slogans fixed on the walls of the tent (one wall general information, one wall wild bees in arable land, one wall wild bees in gardens). • Table with information material • Wild bee specimens projected onto a monitor via a magnifying glass. • Table with Information, pictures and material about the breeding needs of wild bees.
<p>Data collected No collection of data.</p>
<p>Images</p>
<p>Partners AREC Cluster, Aubauernhof</p>
<p>Future plans No future plans outlined.</p>

Soil structure and aggregate stability of different soils

Purpose and goals of activity

Training to learn to assess the structure of different soils and to determine the structure of soil aggregates.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The farmers were asked to bring their own soil cubes from at least one field. The determination of soil structure and aggregate stability was explained using one soil cube. Then, in groups of 2, one soil cube each was determined. At the end of the determination, the structures were compared, the differences in the structures were discussed, as well as the stability of the aggregates. The main aim was to get a feeling for the determination and to visualize the differences using different soils.

Participants

5 cluster farmers were present.

Duration

2-hour workshop in Nov 2022.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- Information material to determine soil structure.
- Information material to determine the stability of soil aggregates.
- [Video](#) to determine soil aggregates by Urs Mauk.

Data collected

The data was entered into a table for personal use.

Images

Partners

Pannatura, Esterhazyplatz 7, 7000 Eisenstadt, <https://pannatura.at/>

Future plans

No future plans outlined.

Ground dweller workshop and Mini-BioBlitz for farmers

Purpose and goals of activity

Get in touch with different types of ground dwellers and species living on or below the soil surface and getting to know methods to identify and monitor them.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

A few weeks before the event, wooden boards were laid out in a field and the soil was repeatedly watered. In the workshop, identification keys for soil animals, beetles and snails were provided and the identification keys were explained. Small groups then turned over a board and identified the animals underneath. The animals were recorded using beaker magnifiers (Becherlupen) and the iNaturalist app. The data was entered into an evaluation sheet, which the participants took with them. The data was not analyzed.

Participants

Cluster farmers, other farmers and participants (20) who visited 150-year celebration of the experimental farm Groß-Enzersdorf.

Duration

1 hour, May 2022

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- iNaturalist app
- [Identification key for soil animals from ENU](#)
- Identification key for beetles and snakes (not available in digital form)

Data collected

The data was entered into a table for personal use.

Images

Partners

Pannatura, Esterhazyplatz 7, 7000 Eisenstadt, <https://pannatura.at/>

Future plans

No future plans outlined.

Earthworm sampling training for farmers and subsequent sampling on own farms

Purpose and goals of activity

Familiarization with the various earthworm's species in arable land. Classification according to species and age (young, sexually mature). Familiarization with a method for assessing earthworms.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

After an introduction of the method, we worked in groups on different fields implementing the protocol.

<p>Participants 6 cluster farmers participated.</p>
<p>Duration 2 hours in April 2022.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protocol for 30 min earthworm sampling
<p>Data collected First, the number of earthworms found on each site were documented in individual paper protocols and then summarized in an Xcel sheet. The data was then discussed directly with the participants on site.</p>
<p>Images</p>
<p>Partners Pannatura, Esterhazyplatz 7, 7000 Eisenstadt, https://pannatura.at/</p>
<p>Future plans No future plans.</p>

Activity briefs – Cazadores de Aguilar Farmer Cluster, Spain

Creators: Gonzalo Varas (FA)

Soil, production and cover vegetation

Purpose and goals of activity

Train farmers on different methodologies for data collection. One of the objectives of this workshop was to show how soil infiltration capacity can be measured using the double ring infiltrometer.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

On March 12, 2024, an event on cover crops, soil and production day was held in Aguilar de la Frontera, aiming to train farmers on different methodologies for data collection. One of the objectives of this workshop was to show how soil infiltration capacity can be measured using the double ring infiltrometer comparing water infiltration in areas with and without cover vegetation. In the demonstration we could see how the capacity for water infiltration into the soil is much higher in those plots with cover crops than in those without cover, hence affected by intensive soil management.

Jornada sobre **FRAMEWORK** capitalising on biodiversity **12 MARZO 24**

Suelo, producción y cubiertas vegetales

Auditorio de los desamparados (Torre del reloj) – Aguilar de la Frontera (Córdoba)

PROGRAMA

18:00 h: Bienvenida a los asistentes

- D. Gonzalo Varas Romero, Facilitador proyecto Framework

18:10 h: Introducción y presentación

- D. Manuel Olmo. Concejal de Educación, Medio Ambiente, Parques y Jardines de Aguilar de la Frontera
- D. Cristóbal Reina Sicilia. Aguilar Farmer Cluster Leader
- D. José Antonio López García. Federación Andaluza de Caza
- D. Eduardo Espino Reyes. Presidente Club y Peña el Coto Aguilar de la Frontera

18:30 h: Olivares Vivos. Biodiversidad y rentabilidad para el olivar.

- D. José Eugenio Gutierrez Ureña. Delegado de SEO/BirdLife en Andalucía y director del proyecto LIFE Olivares Vivos+

19:00 h: Estrategias de manejo de suelo en olivar. Problemática y beneficios

- D^a Ana Leyva Bollero. Titulada Superior. IFAPA Alameda del Obispo

19:30 h: Pausa

19:15 h: Agricultura regenerativa y velocidad de infiltración de las tierras

- D. Manuel Antolín Aguilar. Ingeniero Técnico Agrícola

19:45 h: Cubiertas vegetales: PAC y producción

- D^a Rosa Franco. Fedeprol
- D. Rafael Olmo. Agricultor proyecto Framework

20:15 h: Mesa redonda y clausura de jornadas

Información: gonzalo.varas@fundacionartemisan.com

Participants

30 farmers and 18 other stakeholders

Duration

Brief demonstration in the morning in two plots with and without cover crops (for 10 people) and three hours meeting in the evening.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- Demo of how to use the double ring infiltrrometer

Data collected

The double ring infiltrrometer has a measured size. We put a liter of water in the smallest and water in the biggest. We control the time and the water that it is infiltrate in the soil and know the liters per minutes that can infiltrate the soil.

Images

Double ring infiltrrometer

Partners

Gonzalo Varas (Facilitator-FA), Manuel Olmo (Councillor of Education and Environment Aguilar), José Antonio López (FAC), Cristóbal Reina (FC Leader) and Francisco Javier Rosa (Vice President Hunting Syndicate), José Eugenio Guzmán (SEO/BirdLife in Andalucía and LIFE Olivares Vivos+ director), Ana Leyva Bollero (Researcher from IFAPA Alameda del Obispo), Manuel Antolín (Agricultura engineer), Rosa Franco (Fedeprol) and Rafael Olmo (farmer belonging to the FC).

Aguilar de la Frontera Council: <https://aguilardelafrontera.es/>

Hunters' association: <https://www.cazadoresdeaguilar.es/>

FA: <https://fundacionartemisan.com/>

FAC: <https://fac.es/>

SEO/BirdLife: <https://seo.org/>

IFAPA: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/agriculturaypesca/ifapa/web/personas-estructuras-y-servicios/centros-ifapa/centro-ifapa-alameda-del-obispo>

Fedprol: <https://www.fedeprol.com/>

Future plans

Measurement with autonomous systems of soil temperature and humidity, and olive production.

Activity briefs – Cranborne Chase Farmer Cluster, UK

Creators: Clare Buckerfield (FWAG SW), Ellie Ness and Niamh McHugh (GWCT)

Farmland bird winter feeding and monitoring

Purpose and goals of activity

To install supplementary feeders in hedgerows and fill with two different seed mixes to understand how much these might be used by farmland birds, which birds use them, and what seed mix to use.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Farmers provided with 2 feeders and two different seed mixes – grain based, and a more diverse seed-based finch mix, and a video camera trap for monitoring. Farmers installed feeders and started feeding. After a month the camera trap was put on each feeder for 2 days and set to record 5 secs of video every 5 minutes for 1 hour each day. This was repeated monthly. FWAG SW watched each clip and identified the birds using the feeders. Farmers also were asked to sit and observe the feeders for 30 minutes during the GWCT Big Farmland Bird Count and submit these results to the facilitator.

Participants

6 farmers.

Duration

5 months between Dec 2022-April 2023.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- Winter Feeding Project Guidance
- [The Big Farmland Bird Count Information Sheet](#)

Data collected

Species lists from the camera clips.

Species lists from farmers bird counts.

Feeding dairies – although not kept by all participants.

Images

Partners

[Perdix Wildlife Supplies](#) donated the cameras and cloud storage for videos.

[Cranborn Chase National Landscape](#) funded the feeders and the seed.

Future plans

Farmers were encouraged in the following winter (24/25) to carry on feeding and use the cameras in the cluster to monitor them. The 12 feeders were shared more widely with 12 farmers having one each, and the left-over seed was also shared out to increase the amount of supplementary feeding in the cluster. Farmers did not monitor them effectively, but the feeding was undertaken by most of the 12 volunteers.

Pollinator Identification

Purpose and goals of activity

To train volunteers and farmers on identification of butterflies, bees and hoverflies etc. To introduce the FIT count protocol, part of the UK pollinator monitoring scheme.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Led by expert Entomologist Alex Butler, FWAG SW, with support from cluster facilitator. Presentation on pollinators and identification tips. Then a guided walk around wildflower meadows at Chettle House (2023) and Canada Farm (2024) to find and identify pollinators and to undertake FIT count.

Participants

17 volunteers in 2023 and 2 volunteers and 3 farmers in 2024

Duration

2.5 hours one morning.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- Flower-Insect Timed Count protocol: <https://ukpoms.org.uk/fit-counts>

Data collected

FIT counts submitted to POMS.

Images

Partners

No external partners

Future plans

The refresher event was offered in July 2024 to encourage more surveys. A green lane survey methodology was developed that incorporates FIT counts and volunteers encouraged to use this over the summer. This was shared with the whole volunteer group.

Big farmland bird count and farmland bird ID training

Purpose and goals of activity

To build skills and confidence in farmland bird ID to encourage participation in the GWCT Big Farmland Bird Count in Feb (implemented in years 22, 23 and 24).

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Ellie Ness led an early morning farm walk on a cluster farm and pointed out birds that she saw and heard, explaining identifying characteristics and similar birds they could be mistaken for.

Participants

In 2022 event was for cluster farmers, 6 attended. In 2023 and 2024 event was opened up to citizen science volunteers as well. Had 4 in 2023 and 20 in 2024.

Duration

2 hours for the training. Farmers were then asked to do two 30 min counts on their own farms.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- Information about the count, bird ID guides and count sheets: <https://www.bfbc.org.uk/>

Data collected

Data was submitted direct to GWCT. Farmers were also asked to share data with facilitator in 2024.

Images

Partners

No external partners.

Future plans

Farmers and Cit Sci volunteers will be encouraged to continue participation in the annual count, but no further training planned unless there is specific request in Jan/Feb 2025.

Introduction to arable plants

Purpose and goals of activity

To raise awareness of this often-overlooked suite of plants, with the cluster home to some key species and show these to the group.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Led by local expert Robin Walls, with support from cluster facilitator. Presentation on rare arable plants, specimens to look at and a guided walk to a plot of National Importance, when surveyed in 2022.

<p>Participants 4 volunteers and 1 farmer.</p>
<p>Duration 2.5 hours one morning for the training.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.) No associated protocols, apps and tools.</p>
<p>Data collected Arable plant surveys for the FC care carried out by Robin Walls and Clare Buckerfield (GWCT), not intended for the volunteers or farmers to undertake.</p>
<p>Images</p>
<p>Partners No external partners.</p>
<p>Future plans Continue to cultivate and monitor plots as long as funds are available.</p>

<p>Soil assessment training and earthworm surveys</p>
<p>Purpose and goals of activity To train farmers in a simple method to measure biological activity in soils as part of soil health assessments.</p>
<p>Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers Led by Ellie Ness, GWCT, farmers were shown how to dig a soil pit and sort it to collect the worms. Then how to count and age them.</p>
<p>Participants 5 farmers and 10 volunteers.</p>
<p>Duration 1.5 hours</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AHDB resources for counting and recording earthworms.

Data collected

No data was collected.

Images

Partners

No external partners.

Future plans

Intended as training for farmers to do this on their farms for self-soil health monitoring purposes. The volunteers were local people the farmers had recruited to assist them. No intention to collate data. Farmers encouraged to do this and now forms part of Sustainable Farming Incentive Soil Management Plans so some may be doing it as part of this. Chettle Estate undertook surveys of all their fields and sent some results to the facilitator.

Activity briefs – Kanepi kihlkund Farmer Cluster, Estonia

Creators: Riina Kaasik, Eve Veromann and Silva Vilumets (EMU)

Pitfall trapping protocol for ground dweller observations	
<p>Purpose and goals of activity</p> <p>Knowledge transfer: we have ~280 species of Carabids and ~500 species of Staphylinids and several species are essential biocontrol agents in agricultural landscapes.</p>	
<p>Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers</p> <p>We discussed the benefits of herbaceous field edges and their improvement when sown with native meadow seed mixes. The linkages between plant and insect biodiversity, the use of herbal resources by pests' natural enemies and its impact on pesticide use. Farmers also discussed the new CAP as it includes herbaceous field edges in field area and therefore supports their presence in landscape.</p>	
<p>Participants</p> <p>Farmers (5), organizers (3), student (1)</p>	
<p>Duration</p> <p>One day event in June 2024.</p>	
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protocol for pitfall trapping (see images below) • iNaturalist app 	
<p>Data collected</p> <p>No data collected.</p>	
<p>Images</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>PINNASEPÜÜNISTE kasutamise juhend</p> <p>Pinnasepüünistega saab hinnata maapinnal liikuvate putukate arvukust. Eestis sobib pinnasepüünis eriti just JOOKSIKLASTE ja LÖHTITIBLASTE arvukuse ja mitmekesisuse hindamiseks nii põllul, rohumaal, teeservas kui ka metsas.</p> <p>Vajalikud materjalid</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kogumisnõu – 7–8 cm läbimõõduga ja kuni 10 cm sügavune purk või tops. Materjal ei ole oluline, küll aga soovis liiga suur nõu on löks püünistajatele, roomajatele ja kahepaiksetele. • Katus – takistab vihmavee, taimeosade ja mulla sattumist proovi ning kaitses seda loomade eest. • Säilitusvedelik – soolvesi, piirituse või propüleeni-glikooli* (50–60%) lahus. Kuivades püünistes soovivad röövitud liigid putukad kõiki endast nõrgemad ära. <p>Millaal?</p> <p>Putukate liikumine sõltub nii aastaajast, ilmast kui ka liigist. Hea ülevaate saamiseks võiksid pinnasepüünised olla väljas 1–3 päeva, sõltvalt putukate aktiivsusest.</p> <p>Sõrta võiks 3–4 korda vegetatsiooni- perioodi jooksul, kui aega ja huvi rohkem, siis ka tihedamini. Et võrrelda põldu ja põlluserva, tuleks püünised seada samal ajal mõlemasse kohta.</p> </div> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>Kus ja kuidas?</p> <p>Vali koht, kus taimestik on alale kõige iseloomulikum; põllul paiguta pinnasepüünis tehnooraja kõrval.</p> <p>Kogumisnõu kaeva mulla sisse nii, et ülemine serv oleks maapinnaga tase ja serva äärtele ei jääks tühimikke, ning täida ¼ ulatuses säilitusvedelikuga.</p> <p>Katus paiguta kogumisnõu kohale 5–10 cm kõrgusele.</p> <p>Tühjendamisel kurva kogu sisse läbi õhukese kanga, laota see valgele alusele kohapeal määrimiseks või pane määrimistatud topi, et teha seda hiljem.</p> </div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 20px;"> <p>Loendada või määrata?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kiire ülevaate saamiseks võib putukad lihtsalt üle lugeda või kasutada kiirmäärajat lehe teisel küljel. • Täpsem määramine annab rohkem teavet. Selleks sobivad näiteks "Eesti jooksiklased", "Euroopa putukad", "Putukate viimärge". Hea põhimaterjal on Harry Vähi bakalauree-töö "Eesti mardikate (Coleoptera) sugukondade määrajärg ja selle koostamisest". • Mõimed mobiilirakendused võimaldavad kiiresti, vaid foto põhjal määrata paljusid loomi, sh putukaid. <p>iNaturalist</p> <p>iNaturalist on enim kasutatav mobiilirakendus. See võimaldab kiiresti määrata paljusid liike nii põllul kui ka hiljem arvutis. Rakendus pakub oma piltilaasi põhjal võimalikke liike ja perekondi. Aktiivsed kasutajad on sellel üle 250 000.</p> </div> <div style="margin-top: 20px; background-color: #e0f0e0; padding: 5px;"> <p>Eesti Frameworki klaster alal tehavad vastutusi oiaab siit: https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/framework-estoni-elurikkus-kanepi-kandis</p> <p>Lisa ka enda vastused ja sita teistel märgata elurikkust põllumajandusmaail!</p> </div>	

* Propüleenglikool on värvitu ja lõhnatu aine, kasutatakse kosmeetikas ja toidainetootmisel, duššorganismide ohutu.

Discussion with Farmer cluster members about the importance of landscape diversity, benefits of having unmanaged field.

Partners

No external partners

Future plans

No future plans indicated.

Bumblebee identification - using identification chart and on field training for farmers

Purpose and goals of activity

The objective was to enhance knowledge among local farmers about Estonian bumblebee species and their significant role as pollinators in agriculture. Together with the farmers different pollinators were caught and identified.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

One time event that took place at one of the farmers grounds.

Participants

Farmers (3), other participants (2), students (2)

Duration

One day, July 2023

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- Estonian bumblebees (online resource [link](#) (in Estonian), [link](#) (in English))
- Estonian bumblebee identification card, all participants got their own copies to encourage them to continue with bumblebee identification.
- iNaturalist app

Data collected

Several observations were documented as iNaturalist records.

Images

Eve Veromann and Urmas Sellis identifying a bumblebee.

Partners

No external partners

Future plans

No future plans indicated.

Wildlife photography training

Purpose and goals of activity

Highlighting the importance of photo quality when using different tools for identification and what to keep in mind when taking photos.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Farmers and enthusiasts gathered in Hinnomäe farm where nature photographer Arne Ader introduced nature photography and also highlighting the context in photography. During the walk around Hinnomäe grounds, he also shared fascinating sites and findings, showcasing his passion for biodiversity and its preservation.

Participants

Farmers (3), other participants (2), students (2)

Duration

One day event, July 2022

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- Digital camera or phone with camera
- iNaturalist app
- iNaturalist leaflet

Data collected

No data was collected.

Images

Arne Ader introducing essentials of nature photography and nature enthusiast Peeter Veromann taking photo of dragonfly.

Partners

No external partners

Future plans

No future plans indicated.

Hedgehog monitoring - introduction to protocol and materials for farmers

Purpose and goals of activity

Highlighting the loss of biodiversity. In Estonia it is quite common to argue that everything is fine as the loss is not evident to non-specialist but in the light “when did you last saw...” understanding reaches to more people. Hedgehogs are in decline in most countries they have been observed and due to their appearance, they are easy to recognize.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

We introduced the protocol and prepared one of the tunnels together with farmers, so they see the purpose of all the elements (inkpad, paper, food etc). We prepared 7 tunnels, which were given to all farmers in the event as well as to some cluster farmers who could not attend.

<p>Participants Farmers (3), other participants (2), students (2)</p>
<p>Duration One day training followed by one week survey, July 2022</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hedgehog survey leaflet
<p>Data collected Traps were damaged by wildlife or did not catch any hedgehog attention; farmers did not share pictures of “no hedgehog found”.</p>
<p>Images</p> <p>Riina Kaasik explaining the hedgehog survey to farmers.</p>
<p>Partners No external partners</p>
<p>Future plans No future plans indicated.</p>

Activity briefs – Mostviertel Farmer Cluster, Austria

Creators: Daniela Ablinger (AREC)

iNaturalist project and training for farmers

Purpose and goals of activity

Collection of additional data, sensitization of farmers to their own biodiversity on the farm, show how to use iNaturalist.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

- All farmers met on one FC farm.
- Explanation of how the iNaturalist App can be downloaded, how it is used, how to make photos in an appropriate way and why we need additional monitoring data.
- Hands-on activity: Farmers started monitoring with iNaturalist on the meadows outside
- Time for questions during the field trip
- Final discussion about the monitoring and other agricultural topics

Participants

FC farmers and their family members, 14 participants in total

Duration

One afternoon in May 2022, the activity is ongoing and was picked up in several subsequent events (see other activity briefs).

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- iNaturalist: <https://www.inaturalist.org/>
- iNaturalist manual

Data collected

The data was collected within an iNaturalist Project called “Artenvielfalt im Mostviertler Grünland”. 558 observations have been uploaded by the Farmer Cluster (September 18th, 2024) of 308 different species. 12 members are within the i-Naturalist project. Generally, all iNaturalist data are open access although only the iNat project administrators have access to location data for “obscured” observations.

Images

» Projekte
Bedingungen & Regeln | Diesem Projekt beitreten

Artenvielfalt im Mostviertler Grünland

Statistiken

<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> <p>Insgesamt</p> <p style="font-size: 24px; color: green;">532</p> <p>Beobachtungen »</p> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> <p style="font-size: 24px; color: green;">292</p> <p>Arten »</p> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p style="font-size: 24px; color: green;">12</p> <p>Personen »</p> </div>	<p>Meiste Beobachtungen</p> <table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr><td>	Rot-Klee 6 Beobachtungen																															
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	daniela_abl 93 Beobachtungen																																
	walter_starz 85 Beobachtungen																																
	most4fc 64 Beobachtungen																																
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	Gewöhnlicher Hornklee 7 Beobachtungen																																
	Gemeine Akelei 6 Beobachtungen																																
	Rot-Klee 6 Beobachtungen																																

External partners

BIO Austria: <https://www.bio-austria.at/bio-bauern/niederoesterreich-wien/>

Future plans

Annual Farmer Cluster meeting

Biodiversity farm portraits co-created with farmers

Purpose and goals of activity

The goal is to highlight the special plants, animals, and farmers' contributions to biodiversity and to make these visible to consumers.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The farmers collected photos of the biodiversity in their fields themselves, in places known to them as species rich or simply by opportunity (During the vegetation period 2022 – 2024) In a previous training event, they learned about the functions of i-Naturalist. The facilitator repeatedly encouraged the farmers to upload their observations to i-Naturalist, and they were always supported if they had any questions. The facilitator will put everything together, the information about the Cluster farms and the species and the pictures into a booklet.

Participants

8 FC farmers.

Duration

During the vegetation period, the farmers have been collecting data since 2022.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/home>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/artenvielfalt-im-mostviertler-gruenland>
- See “iNaturalist project and training for farmers “above.

Data collected

The data was collected in the project “Artenvielfalt im Mostviertler Grünland” on iNaturalist. All members of the group have access to it.

Images

The layout of the booklet is still in progress. No pictures are available yet.

Partners

BIO Austria

Future plans

The biodiversity farm portraits can be distributed among consumers and different citizens to show what farmers are doing to maintain and enhance species richness. The farmers should receive a digital form of the booklet each so that they can continue to use this information for themselves and their farm. It is also useful for BIO Austria. The farmers in the FC appear as model farms to show other organic farmers that promoting biodiversity is not that difficult.

Grassland monitoring on newly sown meadows

Purpose and goals of activity

Showing the success of the biodiversity measures.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Farmer Cluster meeting, once or twice a year; Each meeting takes place on a different farm.

The farmers went out across the yard and into the meadows. First, the visitors were given a tour of the farm. The farm is run in a variety of ways. On the one hand, there are the Dexter cattle, which can move freely on the pasture. For grazing, new pieces of meadows are alternately fenced in, depending on what makes sense for the vegetation. The calves are sold on to other breeders. The meat from these cattle is intended for personal use but also for sale. The farm also has a relatively new orchard, with a wide variety of fruits from chestnuts to almonds, as well as some species-rich hedges that serve as windbreaks. The next stop of our Framework Farmer Cluster meeting was the newly created species-rich smooth oatgrass meadows, which were examined in more detail with Walter Starz (AREC) and their progress was interpreted. The first area, which was previously arable land, was re-sown in late summer 2021 with the

species-rich “Renatura smooth oat meadow mixture” from Kärntner Saatbau. In addition to the plant-growing tips for planting and caring for such a population, there was also information about the insects that visit the plants in the oat meadow, such as meadow clary, garden burnet or daisy. For example, wild bees are often more efficient pollinators than honeybees because they are abdominal pollinators. Two further newly created meadows using a reverse rotation tiller and slot seeding were visited. In addition, Kurt Krimberger (AREC) was able to inspire with his ornithological knowledge. The farmers were very interested and there was a lively exchange about birds and measures to promote them.

Participants

9 FC farmers

Duration

8th September 2024, one afternoon

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

Plants were identified and shown to the farmers on the spot without additional aid. Information on the vegetation and management of extensive meadows was discussed verbally. Participants were encouraged to use the iNaturalist app to identify and record species.

Data collected

Data was not actively collected.

Images

Partners

No external partners collaborated in this activity.

Future plans

Reflect on the activity in future FC meetings.

Mostviertel Farmer Cluster meets Salzburger Flachgau

Purpose and goals of activity

Networking of farmers with the same interests regarding biodiversity, new input for measures to promote biodiversity.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

On October 21st, 2023, the farmers of the Mostviertel Farmer Cluster came together to visit the town of Straßwalchen, 163 km away. The reason for this was the information event "Cultural landscape then and

now" as part of the "Diversity on my farm" project, which is managed by ÖKL. The venue was the dairy farm of farmer and biodiversity ambassador Andreas Badinger. After a short welcome, there was a tour of the farm and then the visitors were taken to Andreas' fields and thus had the opportunity to get to know the biodiversity-promoting measures that the farmer himself had implemented on the farm. A wide variety of habitats were created for creatures in and around the grassland, such as fallow strips at the edge of the field, narrow fields with vegetable crops between the fodder areas, or flower strips along the paths. But the habitats were upgraded not only in the fields themselves but also in the border zones between forest and meadow, with a species-rich hedge at the edge of the forest or a very extensively managed old grass strip between the hedge and grassland. In addition, Andreas Badinger attaches great importance to promoting various insects, such as hoverflies and wild bees, by storing waste wood and branches on the edges of paths and forests. The afternoon offered many interesting presentations on topics dealing with the change in agriculture and the cultural landscape in Straßwalchen. The focus was on how humans have changed the landscape and what measures led to biodiversity loss, such as the straightening of rivers or the disappearance of small-scale agricultural family-enterprises. There was then an introduction to the topic of pollinators in grassland and finally the Framework project was presented and its contribution to promoting biodiversity and networking local farmers.

Participants

FC farmers, farmers and interested citizens, about 35 participants

Duration

21st October 2023, all day

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

Speakers and the hosting farmer discussed the biodiversity friendly measures on the farm and showed the insects, flowering strips, herb strips, etc. to the participants. They were encouraged to search on their own for species and habitats to use the iNaturalist app to identify and record species.

Data collected

Data was not actively collected.

Images

Partners

Austrian Board of Trustees for Agricultural Technology and Rural Development (ÖKL)

Future plans

If there are more offers for excursions focusing on biodiversity, the FC will be happy to take part again.

BioBlitz with farmers during Farmer Cluster event at Aubauernhof

Purpose and goals of activity

Sensitization of farmers, neighbors and interested citizens for biodiversity

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

- Designing of an attractive information stand to inform the visitors about the BioBlitz.
- Announce the meeting point and time for the BioBlitz.
- Explanation of the iNaturalist App and distribution of the flyers.
- Interested participants were taken on a cross-country walk across different habitats of the farm.
- Catching insects with nets and showing them via magnifying glass to the group.
- Identifying animals and plants via the iNaturalist App.
- Encouraging farmers to observe and collect biodiversity data using iNaturalist.

Participants

Cluster farmers, and other farmer visitors to the event, 15 participants

Duration

The BioBlitz took place on the 26th May 2023, and lasted about 1.5 hours

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- iNaturalist project: <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/artenvielfalt-im-mostviertler-gruenland>
- Determination aids, iNaturalist flyer, BirtNet flyer, iNaturalist manual

Data collected

The data was collected in the project “Artenvielfalt im Mostviertler Grünland” on iNaturalist. All members of the group have access to it.

Images

Partners

BIO Austria: <https://www.bio-austria.at/bio-bauern/niederoesterreich-wien/>

Future plans

Conduct more BioBlitzes, excursions and Citizen Science activities in the cluster with school kids, farm neighbours, etc.

Activity briefs – Val Graziosa Farmer Cluster, Italy

Creators: Virginia Bagnoni, Camilla Moonen and Alice Caselli (SSSA)

Olive fruit fly monitoring	
Purpose and goals of activity	To train olive growers and make them responsible for controlling the olive fly and improve their knowledge about this important presence in the olive grove.
Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers	The activity took place on three different training days in April, June and July. During the training we had a field walk during which farmers learnt to observe flies on pheromone traps and they were trained on monitoring presence of stings on olives. Finally, they could see how the observations were reported in the app to get an indication of the state of infestation in the olive grove and the prediction of the pest's presence trend. For the farmers not able to be present to the training days we had personal visits to explain the use of traps and app.
Participants	We had a total of 18 participants including 4 farmers from the cluster, 5 other farmers from the area, 1 advisor, 4 researchers, 3 experts and the facilitator.
Duration	The activity took place from April to July 2023, repeated by some farmers in 2024
Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • App Poderi https://poderi.app/#farms • Pheromon traps • A demo video
Data collected	Farmers subsequently contributed to data collection on the olive fruit fly population development and data were entered in the App Poderi.
Images	

Partners

IPMWORKS project (SSSA) <https://ipmworks.net/>

PATH2DEA project (AEDIT srl) <https://www.path2dea.eu/index.html>

Future plans

Some FC farmers decided to continue the activity and have been monitoring and mass-trapping in the 2024 growing season.

Soil biological fertility assessment through QBS method

Purpose and goals of activity

The purpose is to understand whether a waste element, such as olive pomace, can be turned into a resource to improve soil fertility in the olive grove.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

A soil sampling trial in two organically managed olive groves included in the Farmer Cluster with interested farmers who applied olive pomace. Parts of the olive groves were treated with pomace from a mill under organic management and owned by a member of the cluster. The steps to carry out the sampling are as follows:

1. Go to the field and take lumps of soil that are uniform in volume.
2. Bring the soil samples to the laboratory, where funnels, known as Berlese funnels, are installed for the extraction of micro-arthropods.
3. Samples preserved in alcohol are evaluated by an experienced person.
4. Take soil samples to analyse chemical composition and SOM.

Participants

2 farmers included in the cluster together with technicians and experts.

Duration

From spring 2021 to the end of the project. Last sampling will take place on October 2024.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

Farmers were present when samples were taken. A video was made and shared to explain how to take samples. To do this themselves, the Berlese traps would need to be constructed so it is not easy for them to do this entirely by themselves. Results were shared annually during the FC meetings.

Data collected

Data collected and analysed by SSSA. Results shared with farmers.

Images

Partners

No external partners involved.

Future plans

The results are encouraging, and it would be interesting for farmers to know about how to have access to the olive pomace. We may start an investigation with the local olive mill to evaluate how to take advantage of the olive pomace and distribute it correctly, following national and local regulations.

Ground cover diversification and management in olive groves

Purpose and goals of activity

Understand which mowing management method promotes the biodiversity of wild plants in the olive grove as well as facilitating peer to peer exchange about grassing of olive groves advantages in terms of improving soil conditions, variety of vegetation and creating a favourable habitat for olive fly predatory insects such as carabids and staphylinids.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The action includes two distinct activities:

1. A trial taking place on 2 representative plots: one managed by the olive grower according to his idea and needs; the other managed by the olive grower according to different indications. Before and after mowing a vegetation sampling was undertaken by SSSA. While farmers were informed about the details of the monitoring, they did not actively join or engage in the monitoring activity. However, they helped setting up and managing land for the trial.
2. A discussion in which the farmer explained his vision on management, benefits and opportunities of olive grove grassing; followed by a demonstration of different states of vegetation growth as well as a joint identification of species and species diversity in differently managed areas of the farm. The event ended with a joint moment of olive oil tasting.

Participants

The trial started with the participation of 6 farmers and ended with 4 of them.

The peer-to-peer training event 10 participants: 5 farmers (3 from the cluster); 1 researcher; 1 advisor; 1 technician; 2 boys temporarily working in the farm for the alternation school-work project

Duration

The trial took place from April 2023 to April 2024.

The knowledge exchange event took place on 12 June 2024 (half a day).

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

A grass cutting step-by-step guidelines on how to conduct the trial in accordance with farmers ideas and needs (the same for 2023 and 2024).

Data collected

During the trial, data was collected by SSSA using the Qfield app to insert vegetation data <https://qfield.org/>. SSSA has access to the data.

Images

From the peer-to-peer training:

Partners

- No external partners were engaged in the trial.
- The peer-to-peer event was co-organised with the IPMworks project <https://ipmworks.net/>

Future plans

Since one of the FC farmers has acquired a lot of land that includes olive groves within the cluster, it is planned, as a continuation of the cluster activity to implement a new mowing trial with a new scheme that SSSA team is developing with the new company team.

We would like to further encourage FC activities where farmers share knowledge and experience gained during the project with other olive growers.

Local Public BioBlitz 2024

Purpose and goals of activity

Sharing a fun and relaxing field activity to focus participants' attention on the biological diversity of places, in order to raise awareness of the importance of protection and conservation.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The participants were divided in 3 groups who did a walk and gathered at the Parco della Ricordanza (a memorial park to remember the 2018 wildfire that destroyed 1148 ha of woodland and olive groves). During the walk botanical experts supported the observation of the local flora, with special attention for the plants growing on the stone walls. In the Park, entomologists, ornithologists and other experts showed biodiversity in water courses, in the soil and insects and birds hiding in the vegetation. Everyone brought something to eat or drink and this was shared among participants.

Participants

The BioBlitz was attended by 45 people including 2 olive growers from the FC, local community members and citizens of all ages, members of local associations, experts from the Natural History Museum, experts from the Framework project, experts from the ECO-Olives project (University of Vienna).

Duration

Activities took place on 4th of May 2024 and the duration was half a day.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- iNaturalist <https://www.inaturalist.org/>
- Instructions on the use of iNaturalist have been provided in the days prior to the event. Three groups were guided by botanical experts, with stops at five stations where zoological experts described the species observed, ran small workshops and answered questions and curiosities.

Data collected

Data accessible via iNaturalist, also managed by Natural History Museum of Calci, who have 'adopted' the CNC Bioblitz Monte Pisano.

Images

ENTRA NELLA **COMMUNITY PER NATURALISTI**
 E DIVENTA **CITIZEN SCIENTIST**
 PER IL MONTE PISANO

Ti piace esplorare la Natura e fare fotografie? Vuoi dare il tuo contributo alla ricerca condividendo le tue osservazioni con altri osservatori e scienziati in tutto il mondo?
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Per saperne di più sul progetto Framework:
<https://www.framework-biodiversity.eu/>

Partners

- Museo di Storia Naturale dell'Università di Pisa <https://www.msn.unipi.it/>
- Sportello di Agroecologia <https://www.agroecologiaalci.it/>
- Comunità del Bosco del Monte Pisano <https://www.comunitadelboscomontepisano.it/>

Future plans

The involvement of local organisations is going well, and we hope that the FRAMEwork project will leave a mark in this area, and we trust that organisations working in the area will promote other BioBlitzes on Monte Pisano in the years to come. MSN will adopt the City Nature Challenge Bioblitz and in 2025 we will have from 3-6 activities during the CNC period on the entire Pisa Mountain area.

'Wild edibles' walk and training

Purpose and goals of activity

Knowledge of spontaneous edible plants that enrich biodiversity of olive groves to make people reflecting on the possibilities offered by farm diversification in terms of production and activities related to the production process, as well as demonstrating the importance of an approach aimed at optimising the management and conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services on their farms and in their territory.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The event took place in April 2024 and included a lesson by a farmer of the cluster on wild edible plants we were going to explore. This was followed by a walk for observation and identification for which a booklet produced by the farmer and the iNaturalist app were used. During the walk in the olive grove, the plants illustrated in the theoretical talk were collected and used for some preparations. Local oil from the cluster was used and promoted.

Participants

The field walk was attended by 20 people including 4 olive growers, 1 from the cluster, 1 from the control area, 2 from other areas, 3 representatives of 2 local associations (Sportello Agroecologia di Calci, Comunità del Bosco), the FC facilitator to talk about the project, the FC leader from SSSA and 11 citizens.

Duration

The activity took place on 7th April and the duration was half a day

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- iNaturalist <https://www.inaturalist.org/>
- A booklet prepared by the farmer herself guided plants identification during the walk.

Data collected

No data were collected. People collected plants and prepared them at home.

Images

Partners

Silvia Bennucci is the key farmers developing this activity. Sportello Agroecological supported and promoted the action.

Future plans

The inclusion of this initiative in the cluster's activities focused on the farmer, represented the start of a specific action for this farm, which then held other days dedicated to edible plants, officinal plants and dyeing plants with the support and participation of citizens very keen about the topic, but also with the support of the various components of the cluster: representatives of associations, other olive growers included or not in the cluster itself, and members of the Scuola Sant'Anna team.

City Nature Challenge in the Monti Pisani region

Purpose and goals of activity

Active participation of adults and children who discovered the biological diversity of the places in our hills and cluster and shared the importance of its protection and conservation. FC farmers were engaged in setting up and running the event.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

The event included several routes in the Calci area, carried out both in the afternoon and at night, with botanical experts, herpetologists, ornithologists and entomologists accompanying participants and describing the species that people observed along the way to a cluster organic farm, where participants were welcomed with toasted homemade bread and locally produced oil and wine.

Participants

Over a hundred people from the Monte Pisani region attended the event. Three farmers from the cluster were involved and among the participants there were some farmer families from the neighbourhood.

Duration

The activity took place during the afternoon and evening of 29th May 2023.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- iNaturalist <https://www.inaturalist.org/>
- Instructions on the use of iNaturalist have been provided in the previous days and before the walks.

Data collected

430 reports for a total of 199 species were collected using iNaturalist App.

Alice Lelli, a teenager from the region, won the National price for the highest number of observations that were registered during the CNC and she was invited to the Entomological Lab of SSSA to see how entomologists work and receive her price. Subsequently, she has continued collecting data in the region with iNaturalist. One of her observations turned out to be the bryophyte *Asterella Africana*, and her observation was the most northerly observation ever recorded, and the first on mainland Italy. This result was published in BORZIANA 5 – 2024: https://www.herbmedit.org/Borziana/Borziana5_047-058.pdf

Images

Partners

- Successione Ecologica APS <https://www.successionecologica.it/>
- Museo di Storia Naturale dell'Università di Pisa <https://www.msn.unipi.it/it/>
- Sportello Agroecologico <https://www.agroecologiacalci.it/>
- Comunità del Bosco <https://www.comunitadelboscomontepisano.it/>
- Strada dell'Olio dei Monti Pisani <http://stradadellolio.it/>
- National Diversity Future Center <https://www.nbfc.it/>
- Researchers from the ECO-OLIVES project that takes place on the Monte Pisano (Bea Maas, Rym Bakar and Tara Hanf-Dessler).

Future plans

Our plan was to involve local organizations to which we would transfer the task for the following year and the years to come after the end of the project. And this was achieved through a local BioBlitz realized in 2024 and a commitment to participate again in a CNC in 2025.

Activity briefs – Velké Hostěrádky Farmer Cluster, Czech Republic

Creators: Iris C. Bohnet, Kristina Janečková and Jan Trávníček (CULS)

Birds of prey for natural pest control

Purpose and goals of activity

The topic of improving birds of prey populations for biological pest control has been an important topic in the FC since its start in 2021. Several topical meetings and monitoring were held over the years and nest boxes have been installed in 2022 and 2023. In June 2024, a special open field day on biological control of field mice focused on field mice regulation using biological control measures, where repellent plants, such as sorghum are combined with other measures, such as birds of prey, and attracted about 50 participants. The FC had established several bird boxes across the FC area to attract kestrels and other bird species to nest in the area supporting the control of field mice in the long-term.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Presentations Presentation of implemented measures to promote birds of prey in organic farming systems combined with latest scientific results focusing on the effect of repellent plants on field mice populations and their spreading. This approach is presented as an alternative to most common systemic rodenticide used against field mice in Czech Republic - Stuttox.

Participants

50 participants in total, 30 farmers and advisors, ornithologists, scientists.

Duration

One day in June 2024 as part of an ongoing series of activities focused on birds of prey and pest control.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

There are no associated protocols, apps and tools.

Data collected

Monitoring of the boxes installed showed that all of them were nested that spring with successful rearing of the young birds.

Images

Partners

Czech Ministry of Agriculture
 PROBIO obchodní společnost
 Ekofarma PROBIO
 Czech Organics
 Czech Birdlife

Future plans

Scaling up of measures and long-term monitoring are planned to further demonstrate their impact.

Co-development of biodiversity path

Purpose and goals of activity

The biodiversity path was developed to inform visitors of the area about the area’s fauna and flora and about the role the farmers play in its preservation and development. Trees and shrubs were planted along the route to provide resources for pollinators and other wildlife, as well as shade and improved microclimate for the visitors of the path.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

In the beginning of the process, a meeting was held with farmers and other stakeholders in the area to outline information that is important to these stakeholders and that should appear on the information boards. Throughout the development of the boards, stakeholders were consulted about the content and form of the boards. They also provided crucial information, as well as graphic material and photographs. Importantly, farmers also participated in tree planting, and they perform post-planting care of the trees.

Participants

Participants included 4 FC farmers, 2 landowners from the area, the mayors of the village of Velke Hosteradky and Bošovice and a representative from a neighbouring large-scale farming enterprise.

Duration

The development of the boards took approximately 1 year from the [first stakeholder meeting](#) in December 2022 to [board installation and tree planting](#) in December 2023.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

Co-development was carried out face to face using printed and projected maps as discussion devices.

Data collected

The biopath incorporates an iNaturalist project for which biodiversity data can be collected and stored.

Images

Partners

Jihomoravský region, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Ekofarma Probio, Veselá Biofarma, Jasan

Future plans

The biopath is a permanent installation. It is promoted through various media, including the most widely used map portal of the Czech Republic, Mapy.cz. We hope for continued interest of visitors and iNaturalist users.

BioBlitz – Biodiversity path opening

Purpose and goals of activity

To promote to the public the local landscape, biodiversity and relevant farming activities carried out by the first FC in the Czech Republic.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

Visitors, including FC farmers and other farmers from the region, were provided with instructions on how to install the iNaturalist app and the 'project' associated with the biodiversity path on their smart phones at the entrance, i.e., at the start of the walk.

Participants

About 250 people. Many of the people were friends and supporters of the social farm Jasan.

Duration

One-day event on 18th May 2024 at EkofarmaProbio

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- iNaturalist
- iNaturalist project: <https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/prvni-bio-region-velke-hosteradky>

Data collected

Data was collected via iNaturalist app.

Data is stored in the publicly open project (see link above) and on Mapy.cz

Images

More images from the event can be found [here](#) and [here](#).

Partners

Czech organics
EkofarmaProbio
Jasan (social farm)
Friends of the Earth Czech Republic / Hnutí DUHA
Local ornithologists
Municipality of Velké Hořetadky
Vertas Vinery (cluster farm)

Future plans

To be discussed, maybe repeated next year to coincide with the City Nature Challenge or other open day organized by Jason/Ekofarma Probio.

Activity briefs – Zeeasterweg Farmer Cluster, The Netherlands

Creators: Martine Schoone (BoerenNatuur) and Paul van Rijn (UvA)

Farmer-based monitoring in collaboration with Earthwatch Europe
<p>Purpose and goals of activity</p> <p>The aim was to collaborate with Earthwatch Europe on testing monitoring tool prototypes, developed especially for farmers.</p> <p><u>Soil fauna:</u> This is a simple method to discover which animals live on and in the soil on your farm. Expected groups are snails, millipedes, beetles, worms, woodlice, spiders and ants. On a farm, beetles - especially ground beetles - and spiders are useful because they reduce many harmful insects (such as snails, caterpillars and insects that attack the roots of crops). Woodlice and millipedes help to convert dead organic material into organic matter for the soil.</p> <p><u>Insects transect:</u> Many agricultural crops are largely dependent on wild pollinators such as bees, butterflies, bumblebees and hoverflies for their pollination. The presence of these flying insects is a good indicator of biodiversity. In addition, non-flying insects on crops are important, because they often eat pests. These pest controllers are, for example, beetles and hoverfly larvae. With a 'transect count' you can map the pollinators and pest controllers present on your land.</p> <p><u>Bird point count:</u> The bird point count was developed as a simple way to make a statement about the birds present on a farm. No extensive knowledge of species is required. With this method you get a good idea of how many birds are present on the farm at a certain time. Birds can be helpful because many birds are natural predators that eat caterpillars. Great tits, blue tits and tree creepers, for example, like to eat the oak processionary caterpillar.</p>
<p>Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers</p> <p>9 farmers, including 5 farmers from the FW FC are testing some of the monitoring tools from Earthwatch. The FW FC farmers are in test group 2, and we test 3 different monitoring tools, namely a soil animal test, an insect transect, and a bird point count described above. For soil fauna, 6 tiles are placed in the field 2 weeks prior to the count (3 for productive field and 3 for non-productive field, such as a field edge). The tiles are then lifted, and assessments are made based on the soil fauna search card. The counting results are entered digitally via a smartphone app. During the insect transect, the intention is to count for 10 minutes (5 minutes there and 5 minutes back) along a productive field and a non-productive field. On the way there, the flying insects are counted (hover flies / bees / bumblebees / butterflies and butterflies white) and on the way back the non-flying insects are counted on plants / crops (beetle species / eggs). Finally, birds are counted using a point count. There are 4 counting points (productive field / rest crop / natural element / yard). The count must be carried out max. 2 hours after sunrise and only general species groups are counted (field birds / shrubland birds / song / birds of prey / seagulls / migratory birds).</p>
<p>Participants</p> <p>Nationwide 30 farmers are participating in the test phase. In Flevoland 9 are participating, of which 5 farmers from the FRAMEwork Farmer Cluster Zeeasterweg.</p>
<p>Duration</p> <p>The farmers tested 3 different monitoring tools in 2 weeks and again a month later. In June and July 2024.</p>
<p>Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification card (pollinators) • Identification card (soil fauna, ground-dwellers) • The Earthwatch protocols are not yet openly available as they are still under development.
<p>Data collected</p> <p>The data from the test monitoring was collected in an app developed by Earthwatch and is still in development. Earthwatch has access to the test data.</p>

Images

Partners

Earthwatch Europe <https://farming.earthwatch.org.uk/pages/about-farming-with-nature>

Future plans

In 2025 there will be another round of tests, and the same farmers are planning to participate again.

Introduction to BIMAG moth monitoring

Purpose and goals of activity

The goal was getting to know the BIMAG initiative and learn how to observe moths at night. Since 2019, LTO Noord, BoerenNatuur and De Vlinderstichting have been working together within the Farmer Insect Monitoring Agricultural Area (BIMAG) project. Within the project, 115 enthusiastic farmers have counted moths and butterflies on their farms over the past four years. They collected important

information about the butterfly population in the countryside. BIMAG will be continued over the next five years and we want to monitor butterflies with 150 agricultural companies every year.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

On Thursday 18 July, 2024 we were guests at the Waalkens family farm on the Zeeasterweg in Lelystad. With a compact group of interested parties including members, non-members and citizens we started the evening with a visit to the bird field of the Van der Weele family. A bird field consists of strips with a protein-rich crop such as alfalfa or red clover, alternating with strips consisting of grains and herbs. A bird field is rich in mice and insects. The bird field was developed by the [Foundation Working Group Montagu's Harrier](#), a knowledge centre for farmland birds (Stichting Werkgroep Grauwe Kiekendief). Bird fields are intended for mouse-eating birds of prey and owls, such as the Montagu's harrier, short-eared owl and barn owl, but breeding skylarks and wintering field birds such as meadow pipit, linnet and yellowhammer are also attracted by bird fields. This first-year bird field looked beautiful, and many different herbs were in full bloom. A great opportunity to introduce more people to the ANLb. Upon returning to the Waalkens family farm, Rik Wever from the Butterfly Foundation (BIMAG) gave a presentation about moths, in which he discussed the number of species and the role they play in the rural area. For example, many moths are good pollinators of various crops. After the presentation, a large white cloth with a strong UV lamp was placed next to the canal on the farm and we waited for the first butterflies. We saw many nice species, including some rare ones, and at the end of the evening (around 1 a.m.) the counter was at about 60 species. A nice result and a nice ending to this pleasant and interesting evening. [Short video](#) summary of the evening.

Participants

There were 7 farmers, 5 citizens and 2 experts present.

Duration

July 18, 2024, from 8pm to 1am at night.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

The species and numbers of moths observed during this evening are registered in waarneming.nl (part of <https://observation.org/> and at the Butterfly Foundation. The Dutch version of observation.org is publicly accessible, everyone can add observations of all observed flora and fauna. Experts check the entered data.

Images

Data collected

Moths found during this evening (Names in Dutch)

Blauwooggrasmot

Bleke grasmot

Crème kijkgaatje

Distelbladroller

Donker brandnetelkapje

Dromedaris

Duikermot

Duinmosmot

Egale rietboorder

Egelskopmot

Gamma-uil

Geelbruine rietboorder

Gestippelde houtvlinder

Getekende biesbladroller

Gewone bandspanner

Gewone grasmot

Gewone stofuil

Grijze stipspanner

Haarbos

Halmrupsvlinder / Weidehalmuiltje

Heremietuil
 Huismoeder
 Hyena
 Kameeltje
 Kleine beer
 Kleine boogbladroller
 Kleine huismoeder
 Kokermot onbekend
 Koolmotje
 Kroosvlindertje
 Leverkleurige bladroller
 Lichte spitskopmot
 Loofboombbladroller
 Moerasgrasuil
 Paardenbloemspanner
 Parelmoermot
 Rietmot
 Rode knopbladroller
 Schaduwfruitbladroller
 Schaduwsnuituil
 Smalvleugeldwergspanner
 Stompvleugelgrasuil
 Topbladroller
 Tweekleurig knoopvlekje
 Variabele granietmot
 Vogelkersstippelmot
 Wapendrager
 Zandhalmuiltje
 Zomerbladroller
 Zuringpalpmot

Partners

BIMAG, the butterfly foundation, <https://www.vlinderstichting.nl/bimag/>

Future plans

Farmers who are already participating in BIMAG will continue, and more farmers from Flevoland may join.

Monitoring with insect pan traps at Flevoland Bloeit

Purpose and goals of activity

“Flevoland Bloeit” is a biyearly event organised by Flevolands Agrarisch Collectief/BoerenNatuur to inform farmers and policy makers about policies and methods for nature-inclusive farming in Flevoland, and the role of BoerenNatuur. The purpose of the activity during the June 2023 event was to inform farmers and others about the relationship between nature-inclusive farming and natural pest control and about methods to monitor natural enemies.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

At this event, University of Amsterdam (UvA) and BoerenNatuur hold a stand where farmers were shown how to monitor natural enemies with pan and pitfall traps. Advice was also provided on the type of plant

species that are suitable to support natural enemies of common pests (both herbs and woody vegetation). Monitoring data from the FC were highlighted at the event.

Participants

Farmers and policy makers from province and municipalities of Flevoland were invited. About 20 farmers and 20 other participants visited the stand.

Duration

One afternoon on 22 June 2023.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

- A pan trap station with pans in 3 different colours was installed.
- Laminated sheets with pictures of common natural enemies of pests and suitable flowers were displayed on tables.

Data collected

No data were collected.

Images

Partners

Flevolands Agrarisch Collectief

Wageningen University & Research (WUR): tools for farmers to learn which plants support natural pest control: [Ontsluiten kennis Functionele Agrobiodiversiteit - WUR](#)

Future plans

No future plans.

National Bee counting day and wild bee identification

Purpose and goals of activity

- Inform citizens and farmers about different indicator types and monitoring mechanisms of the FRAMEwork project.

- Train farmers and citizens how to recognize wild bees.
- Inform farmers and citizens about waterfront project.
- Inform farmers and citizens about agricultural nature management and agro-biodiversity.
- Disseminating flower seed mixes that benefit wild bees.

Description of activity, implementation on-site/with farmers

On Saturday 23 April, 2022, the FAC organised the kick-off for the national bee count at Hoeve Vredeveld in Lelystad. Both farmers and citizens were taken into the field by experts and explained how to recognise bees. The Place To Bee explained how the farmyard can be improved so that more bees can live on the farm. Various FAC projects that contribute to more nature were also explained. For example, researchers from the University of Amsterdam were present for the European biodiversity project Framework and participants from the waterfront project were present. Afterwards, participants were able to recognise and count bees in their own garden or on their own farm with more knowledge.

Participants

There were 7 experts, 20 farmers and more than 20 citizens present.

Duration

This activity took place on a Saturday afternoon from 10:00 to 13:00. The bee counting day is an annual event that is currently organized by Naturalis, IVN Nature Education and LandschappenNL. The goal is to learn as much as possible about bees, so that we can help the bee better. The National Bee Count is organized in collaboration with EIS Knowledge Center Insects and Waarneming.nl.

Associated protocols, apps and tools (cameras, sensors etc.)

Apps:

- iNaturalist <https://www.inaturalist.org/>
- ObsIdentify <https://observation.org/apps/obsidentify/>

Data collected

Participants were encouraged to document observations and enter data directly to the platform of <https://www.nationalebijentelling.nl/>

Images

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- Location: Hoeve Vredeveld farm <https://hoevevredeveld.nl/>
- National Bee Count: <https://www.nationalebijentelling.nl/>
- Recognizing bees: Jeroen de Rond (Natural Media)
https://www.naturalmedia.nl/EN/pags_jdr/research/publications/overview_publications_jdr.html
- Place to Bee: <https://theplacetobee.nl/the-place-to-bee/>
- Wateredge project
- Flevolands Agrarisch Collectief, now called BoerenNatuur Flevoland:
<https://boerennatuurflevoland.nl/>

Future plans

No future plans.